

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF BEE COLONIES

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Abstract. *In the article, indicators such as the productivity of bee colonies, honey production, and their economic efficiency were studied and analyzed based on comparative experiments.*

Keywords: *bee, sugar syrup, honey, production, protein feed, bee colony, indicators, costs, income, profitability, net profit, economic efficiency.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is widely acknowledged that the economic efficiency of the industry producing high-quality honey and beekeeping products depends on the bee breed, variety, care and maintenance technology, natural and climatic conditions, season, natural food sources, off-season feeding, colony age and size, compliance with veterinary and sanitary regulations, and other factors [2, 3, 4]. For improving the economic efficiency of breeding and maintaining bee colonies in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to properly prepare them for wintering in the second half of August, September, and October, as the main losses in beekeeping occur in winter and average 12-14% of the total number of colonies [5, 6].

Colonies that survive a harsh winter cause significant damage to beekeeping, while bee diseases, in turn, hinder the development of the industry. Caron, D.M., and Connor, L.J. (2013), Krivsov, N.I., Lebedev, V.I. (2001), Brandor, A.Z. (2012), Korolev V.P. (2012), Kurchavenkov A.B. (2012), Nuzhdin A.S. (2005), Skvorsov A.I. (2011), Turaev O.S. (2010), Eshadavlatov O.Z. (2021), Nurmurodova N.F. (2025). One of the reasons for the low winter survival of bees is that during the winter, bees are unable to leave the hive to clean their intestines; feces accumulate in their large intestine, increasing the fecal load in the intestines, which leads to diarrhea and even death. The main aspect of beekeeping is the preservation of bee colonies during the winter, when bees are closely grouped and their activity decreases. Mannapov A. G., Larionova O. S., Smolnikova E. A. (2011), Khudaiberdiev A. A. (2020), Kononenko E. A., Moreva L. Ya. (2021), Ishmuratova N. M., Tambovsev K. A. (2021).

Beekeeping primarily requires the production of large quantities of high-quality products, increased income, and net profit by reducing production costs. Numerous studies have shown that the main factors for increasing bee colony productivity are raising queen bees in early spring, forming bee colonies and producing bee packages, intensive feeding methods, and improving economic efficiency [13, 14, 15]. It is important to conduct scientific research into the scientific foundations of technologies that accelerate bee colony maintenance and increase their productivity.

II. RESEARCH MATERIAL AND METHOD.

The study was conducted from 2023 to 2025 at the educational and experimental farm of the TDAU in the Kibray district of the Tashkent region, experimental group 1 in the Bustonlyk district of the Tashkent region, and experimental group 2 at apiaries in the Parkent district of the Tashkent region [4]. The data obtained were statistically processed using the Student's t-test,

according to the method of E.K. Merkureva (1970, 1991), and the significance level (R). The calculations were correlated on a computer using MS OFFICE (Microsoft Excel).

III. RESULTS OF THE STUDY.

For implementing the results of our study in production, it is also important to study their economic effectiveness. For this purpose, we examined the economic efficiency of our study. Therefore, special attention was paid to the processes of transplanting bee colonies and the efficient use of their honey collection capacity. All farm conditions were taken into account for the growth and development of bee colonies in the experiment. The costs of establishing and replanting one bee colony were calculated. We assessed the economic efficiency of the experimental and control groups based on production costs per season at 2023-2025 prices. The data are presented in Tables 1, 2, and 3.

Table 1

Economic efficiency of the studies.

№	Indicators	2023 year		
		The groups of bee colonies in the experiment are n-10.		
		1- experimental group	2- experimental group	control group
1	Purchase of a beehive, soums	4000000	4000000	4000000
2	Purchase of equipment and supplies used for beekeeping, soums	600000	600000	600000
3	Purchase of medicines against bee pests and diseases, soums	400000	400000	400000
4	Feed consumption for 120 days, soums	4460000	4460000	4260000
5	Costs of relocating bee colonies, soums	500000	500000	-
6	Total production costs, soums	9960000	9960000	9260000
7	Honey production, kg	186	164	142
8	Selling price of 1 kg of honey, soums	70000	70000	70000
9	Revenue from honey sales, soums	13020000	11480000	9940000
10	Net profit, soums	3060000	1520000	680000
11	Profitability ratio, %	30,7	15,2	7,3

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, in 2023, 3060000 soums were earned from the first experimental group, 1520000 soums from the second experimental group, and 680000 soums from the control group. The profitability level was 30.7% in the first experimental group, 15.2% in the second experimental group, and 7.3% in the control group. The first experimental group was 15.5% higher than the second experimental group and 23.4% higher than the control group. In 2023, equipment and supplies used for beehives and beekeeping were purchased. Despite this, high income was received from bee colonies in all groups.

Table 2

Economic efficiency of the conducted studies.

№	Indicators	2024 year		
		The groups of bee colonies in the experiment are n-10.		
		1- experimental group	2- experimental group	control group
1	Buy rum, soums	1500000	1500000	1500000
2	Purchase in Mumpar, soums	1200000	1200000	1200000
3	Purchase of medicines against bee pests and diseases, soums	500000	500000	500000
4	Feed consumption for 120 days, soums	5825000	5825000	5625000
5	Costs of relocating bee colonies, soums	500000	500000	-
6	Total production costs, soums	9525000	9525000	8825000
5	Honey production, kg	184	170	151
6	Selling price of 1 kg of honey, soums	75000	75000	75000
7	Revenue from honey sales, soums	13800000	12750000	11325000
8	Net profit, soums	4275000	3225000	2500000
9	Profitability ratio, %	44,9	33,8	28,3

According to Table 2, in the 2024 economic efficiency analysis, the first experimental group outperformed the second experimental group. The first experimental group earned 4,275,000 soums, the second experimental group earned 3,225,000 soums, and the control group earned 2,500,000 soums in net profit. The profitability rate was 44.9% in the first experimental group, 33.8% in the second experimental group, and 28.3% in the control group. The first experimental group outperformed the second experimental group by 11.1% and the control group by 16.6%.

Table 3

Economic efficiency of the studies.

№	Indicators	2025 year		
		The groups of bee colonies in the experiment are n-10.		
		1- experimental group	2- experimental group	control group
1	Buy rum, soums	1500000	1500000	1500000
2	Purchase in Mumpar, soums	1200000	1200000	1200000
3	Purchase of medicines against bee pests and diseases, soums	500000	500000	500000
4	Feed consumption for 120 days, soums	5825000	5825000	5625000

5	Costs of relocating bee colonies, soums	600000	600000	-
6	Total production costs, soums	9625000	9625000	8825000
5	Honey production, kg	190	182	160
6	Selling price of 1 kg of honey, soums	80000	80000	80000
7	Revenue from honey sales, soums	15200000	14560000	12800000
8	Net profit, soums	5575000	4935000	3975000
9	Profitability ratio, %	57,9	51,3	45

It should be emphasized that Table 3, which presents economic indicators for 2025, shows that in the third year, the first experimental group earned 5,575,000 soums in net profit, the second experimental group earned 4,935,000 soums, and the control group earned 3,975,000 soums. The profitability rate was 57.9% in the first experimental group, 51.3% in the second experimental group, and 45% in the control group. In the first experimental group, this indicator was 6.6% higher than in the second experimental group and 12.9% higher than in the control group. The results of our study, taken from the works of N. I. Krivsov, V. I. Lebedev (2001), A. Z. Brandorf (2012), A. G. Mannapov, O. S. Larionova, E. A. Smolnikova (2011), A. A. Khudaiberdiev (2020), O. Z. Eshdavlatov (2021), and N. F. Nurmurodova (2025), are consistent with the results obtained during scientific research. The authors studied the economic efficiency of honey production obtained from bee colonies of different breeds.

IV. CONCLUSIONS.

According to the results of scientific research, the productivity of the first experimental group of Krajina bees was high in all three years. The data obtained showed that feeding bee colonies with protein feed in spring and autumn, as well as the use of Krajina and Carpathian bees in beekeeping farms, is economically feasible.

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